
Research Article

A new combination in *Metastelma* (Apocynaceae)

Rajeev Kumar Singh

Botanical Survey of India, Arid Zone Regional Centre, AIIMS Road, Jodhpur - 342014, Rajasthan, India

E-mail: rksbsiadsingh@gmail.com; ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0136-9243>

Article Details: Received: 2026-01-24 | Accepted: 2026-06-10 | Available online: 2026-06-16

Licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License

Abstract: The morphological characters described in the protologue of *Cynanchum cuspidatum* Hook. & Arn. (≡ *Cynanchum hookerianum* Steud.) support its placement in the genus *Metastelma* R.Br. Accordingly, a new combination is proposed.

Keywords: Brazil, *Cynanchum cuspidatum*, *Cynanchum hookerianum*, Lectotype, *Metastelma cuspidatum*

Introduction

Metastelma R.Br. comprises about 94 species, distributed in tropical and subtropical America (POWO, 2026). In Brazil, the genus is represented by seven species, namely *M. ditassoides* Schltr., *M. giuliettianum* Fontella, *M. harleyi* Fontella, *M. hirtellum* (Oliv.) Liede, *M. hookerianum* (Steud.) R.Kr.Singh, *M. myrtifolium* Decne. and *M. parviflorum* (Sw.) R.Br. ex Schult. (POWO, 2026). Except *M. hirtellum* and *M. parviflorum*, all other are endemic to Brazil. The vegetative and floral characters of *Cynanchum cuspidatum* Hook. & Arn. (≡ *Cynanchum hookerianum* Steud.), as presented in the protologue, correspond to those of *Metastelma* R.Br. Therefore, a new combination is proposed herewith. In addition, lectotype is designated here for the name *Cynanchum hookerianum* Steud. in accordance with the guidelines and recommendations of Article 9 of the International Code of Nomenclature for algae, fungi, and plants (Turland et al., 2025).

New combination

Metastelma hookerianum (Steud.) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Cynanchum cuspidatum* Hook. & Arn., J. Bot. [Hooker] 1: 293. 1835, *nom. illeg., non* Thunb., Observ. Cynanch. 6. 1821. *Cynanchum hookerianum* Steud., Nomencl. Bot. [Steudel], ed. 2, 1: 462. 1841.

Metastelma cuspidatum (Hook. & Arn.) Decne., Prodr. [A.P. de Candolle] 8: 516. 1844, *nom. illeg. et superfl.*

Figure 1: Lectotype of *Cynanchum hookerianum* Steud. (K000096344, © The Trustees of the Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew)

Lectotype (designated here or perhaps holotype): Brazil, South Brazil, Woods of Lagoa, s.d., Tweedie 221 (K000096344!, Figure 1).

Distribution: Brazil (South Brazil).

Acknowledgements

The author is grateful to the Director, Botanical Survey of India, Kolkata and the Head of Office, Botanical Survey of India, Arid Zone Regional Centre, Jodhpur for providing the facilities. The author also thanks the Curator of K for making the image of the type specimen available online.

References

- POWO. (2026). Plants of the World Online. Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew. Available from: <http://www.plantsoftheworldonline.org/> (accessed 15 January 2026).
- Turland, N.J., Wiersema, J.H., Barrie, F.R., Greuter, W., Hawksworth, D.L., Herendeen, P.S., Knapp, S., Kusber, W.-H., Li, D.-Z., Marhold, K., May, T.W., McNeill, J., Monro, A.M., Prado, J., Price, M.J. and Smith, G.F. (2018). International Code of Nomenclature for algae, fungi, and plants (Shenzhen Code). *Regnum Vegetabile* 159. Koeltz Botanical Books, Glashütten. <https://doi.org/10.12705/Code.2018>